

First Law of Thermodynamics and Indistinguishability of Energy and Volume

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The first law of thermodynamics, written in the form $dE = dQ - dW$ ((1)), has the form of a conservation of energy equation in which there are two types of energy. One, dW , is based on mechanical work or the changes of a parameter such as volume, while the other, dQ , is heat which shows that a system may absorb photons (as an example) and gain energy without an external parameter having to change. The equilibrium differential form, however, $dE = TdS(T,V) - PdV$ ((2)) is different because the term $TdS(T,V)$ for an ideal gas contains both T and V and leads to both dT and dV terms, with the dV term canceling $-PdV$ for an ideal gas for which $E(T)$.

Given the conservation of energy form of the first instance and concepts like dE and $-PdV$, it may seem surprising to see a $TdS(T,V)$ term which does not seem to be linked with classical mechanics.

We argue that the mechanical terms dE and dV are directly linked to TdS which is $T \ln$ maximum number of states through the idea of indistinguishability of energy and volume. Energy and volume are ideas existing in classical mechanics which do not require a statistical interpretation. Even average energy $E_{ave} = \sum_i e_i f(e_i)$ for an arbitrary $f(e_i)$ probability distribution differs from the concept of indistinguishability and maximum number of states. We suggest that indistinguishability in E and V means that there are no constraints which "distinguish".

In the case of volume, a particle can be at any point in V with the same probability. Even though V is extensive, one does not assign an amount of volume to a particle as one assigns a single particle energy, e_i . If TdS is to cancel $-PdV$ and $PV = nRT$ then S contains a term proportional to $\ln(V)$ and this is \ln of the maximum number of volume states.

In the case of energy, indistinguishability appears because $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ means that for an ideal gas: $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$. As a result, in the special indistinguishable (maximum number of states picture), a classical mechanical parameter, e_i , becomes linked to probability $f(e_i)$ through $e_i = -T \ln(f(e_i))$ for an unnormalized $f(e_i)$. The point is that an average energy expression is then linked to $\ln(f \text{ power } f)$, but this in turn is linked to the number of states, as we show. Thus, $E(\text{average})$ and the maximum number of states are closely linked. We suggest that one may consider ((2)) as a relationship between a statistical quantity, the \ln of number of states in the special case of indistinguishability or maximum number of states, to classical mechanics quantities, dE_{ave} and $-PdV$.

The Ideal Gas Situation

Imagine an ideal gas for which total energy does not depend on volume, but only on a parameter temperature T . To describe such a gas, one uses the notion of indistinguishability or maximum number of states if one states that a particle may be anywhere in the volume V with the same probability. Even without knowing $f(e_i)$, one may write:

$$E_{ave} = \sum_i e_i f(e_i) \quad ((3))$$

and note that pressure from a single particle is $b e_i f(e_i)$, where b is a constant because impulse is proportional to p and flux is proportional to v . Thus, one expects uniform pressure everywhere, so:

$$\text{Pressure} = P \text{ proportional to } E_{ave}/V \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Thus: } -PdV \text{ proportional to } d(\ln(1/V)) = -dV/V \quad ((5))$$

Here $\ln(V)$ equals the \ln of the number of position states available, but one would not normally think of it in such a manner in classical mechanics.

Given $dE(T)$ and the classical mechanical notion of work $-PdV$ (which depends on V , while dE does not), one requires a math function $G(V,T) dS(T,V)$ in order that:

$$dE(T) = G(V,T) dS(T,V) - PdV \quad ((6))$$

Using $PV=nRT$ for an ideal gas (which follows from experiment, but may also be derived for the maximum number of states picture: If this is the case, then $E = \text{constant } T$ because P and E differ by a numerical constant.

$$G(V,T) dS/dT \text{ partial} = dE \quad \text{and} \quad G(V,T) dS/dV \text{ partial} = P$$

Using $S = \ln(V)$ and $G(V,T) = nRT$, one then has:

$$nRT dS/dT \text{ partial} = dE \quad ((7))$$

One possible solution for ((7)) is to have a factor of S be $\ln(E^{\text{power}(d1)})$ where $d1$ is a constant. Then, holding V constant,

$$NR T d \ln(E^{\text{power } d1}) = NRT d1 dE/E, \text{ so if } NR d1T = E, \text{ then}$$

((7)) is satisfied.

Now, $\ln(V)$ was said to represent the \ln of the number of volume states so one might suggest that $\ln(E_{ave})$ is linked to the number of energy states, but why should that be the case?

Indistinguishability of Energy

$E_{ave} = \text{Sum over } i f(e_i) e_i$ and in general $f(e_i)$ may be any set of probability. It does not need to represent a maximum number of states or indistinguishability. We suggest that the maximum number of states is equivalent to indistinguishability (because one minimizes constraints). This means that a classical mechanical parameter, e_i , now becomes an indistinguishable quantity in probability because for $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$, $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$.

In other words, the classical mechanical quantity e_i is almost the probability, i.e. $-e_i/T = \ln(f(e_i))$.

The point is that general average equations using $e_i f(e_i)$ are now proportional to:

$$\ln(f(e_i)) f(e_i) \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{The key of ((8)) is that } \ln(f(e_i)) f(e_i) = \ln(\exp(f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))) \quad ((9))$$

For a set of $f(e_i)$, one expects $Nf(e_i)$ occurrences of e_i for large N . Then:

$$\text{Probability of an } N \text{ run} = \text{Product over } i \exp(f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i)) \quad ((10))$$

$$\ln(\text{prob}) = \text{Sum over } i f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i)) \quad ((11))$$

Given that $\ln(f(e_i))$ is proportional to e_i , ((11)) is proportional to E_{ave} , but at the same time

$$\ln(\text{prob}) = \ln(1/ \text{Number of states}) \quad ((12))$$

for the maximum number of states (indistinguishability case).

Thus, there is a double meaning in E_{ave} . It is the usual average of a classical mechanical quantity, e_i , but at the same time is the \ln of the maximum number of states.

As a result, we suggest that in the case of a maximum number of states or indistinguishability, this indistinguishability is for V and e_i 's and so a function linked to the maximum number of states (e.g. $\ln(\text{maximum number of states})$) may be related to classical mechanical type terms such as dE_{ave} and $-PdV$. In other words, we suggest that the first law of thermodynamics, written as ((2)), is really an equivalence statement of two classical mechanical type terms, $-PdV$ and dE_{ave} , and a statistical number of states term. This equivalence is possible because of the idea of indistinguishability.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the first law of thermodynamics, written as (1), implies conservation of energy and suggests two different modes of energy change. One is the usual work term from classical mechanics and the second is a heat term which is physically apparent when photons are absorbed, but V kept constant. In the differential equation form, however, $S(V,T)$ even though $E(T)$, so $dS(V,T)$ is not simply the picture of photons being absorbed with V being held constant. Rather, one may see using $PV = nRT$ that S may contain a $\ln(V)$ piece as well as a piece with no V . $\ln(V)$ is the \ln of the number of volume states. The second S piece needs to be linked to E_{ave} . One might suggest then that E_{ave} is associated with the maximum number of energy states, but how is such an association made? We suggest that in the case of a maximum number of states there should be indistinguishability of e_i 's, namely that for $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$, $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$. This leads to $f=\exp(-e_i/T)$ and suggests that the term $e_i f(e_i)$ from E_{ave} is equivalent to $f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$. This latter term may be shown to be linked to $\ln(\text{probability for } N$

particles) which in turn is proportional to $\ln(1/\text{number of states})$. Using $f=\exp(-e_i/T)$ means that one is considering the maximum number of states.

Thus, we suggest that the first law of thermodynamics, written as ((2)), implies a relation between the maximum number of states, i.e. an indistinguishability scenario, with two classical mechanical type terms, dE_{ave} and $-PdV$.